

Performance Analysis of a Deep Neural Network-Based Spectrum Sensing Approach

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Abstract. Radio spectrum is a limited resource and the traditional fixed spectrum allocation methods which permit only the Primary Users (PUs) to access the allocated spectrum, even when it is idle, will quickly deplete the radio resources. The growing network demands and emerging 6G applications, like Intelligent Healthcare, call for the effective utilization of the underutilized spectrum. Dynamic Spectrum Management (DSM) is a spectrum allocation approach which with the help of Spectrum Sensing (SS) detects and transmits in the underutilized frequency bands. Deep Neural Networks (DNNs)-based SS techniques being data-driven can enhance the performance of 6G communication systems by eliminating the drawbacks of conventional SS approaches which suffer from missed detection of the PU, and traditional Machine Learning (ML) techniques which need manual feature extraction. This article explores the publicly available RadioML 2016.10A dataset and demonstrates the use of a Deep Learning (DL)-based SS approach on a dataset formed by using the RadioML 2016.10A samples and synthetically generated noise. SS is considered as a binary classification problem and the proposed deep autoencoder-based technique reports a 97.41% classification accuracy on the entire dataset. The performance of the model is analyzed for various Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) values and the model achieves high classification accuracies. The proposed algorithm when analyzed for different modulation schemes reports a 100% test accuracy for 8-Phase-Shift Keying (8PSK), Binary Phase-Shift Keying (BPSK), Quadrature Amplitude Modulation-16 (QAM16), and Pulse Amplitude Modulation-4 (PAM4) schemes.

Keywords: Autoencoders, Cognitive Radio, Deep Learning, Deep Neural Networks, Spectrum Sensing

1 Introduction

With the growth in network demands and the emergence of 6G applications like Internet of Everything, Intelligent Healthcare and Industry 5.0, the demand for radio resources is continuously increasing and has resulted in a shortage of the frequency spectrum [1], [2]. The traditional static spectrum allocation methods permit only the licensed or Primary Users (PUs) to access the allocated spectrum. The unlicensed Secondary Users (SUs) cannot access the radio resources of the PU even when they are idle [3]. To prevent the denial of urgent radio requirements it is essential that the underutilized spectrum bands are fully utilized [2]. Dynamic Spectrum Management (DSM) is a spectrum management approach that detects the vacant frequency bands of the PUs with the help of Spectrum Sensing (SS) and allows the SUs to transmit in those underutilized bands.

Conventional SS methods such as energy detection and cyclostationary-based detection suffer from false alarms and missed detection of the PU [4]. To eliminate these drawbacks of conventional SS approaches, traditional Machine Learning (ML) algorithms such as naïve bayes classifier and support vector machines have been used in several research works to enhance the sensing performance [5], [6]. However, traditional ML methods involve the time-consuming manual feature extraction process which requires the knowledge of field experts. Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) are data-driven algorithms that can make optimal use of the non-linearities of the training data and extract complex patterns from the input data to enhance detection performance [7]. In this work we treat SS as a binary classification problem and propose a DNN-based SS approach to classify a dataset formed from RadioML 2016.10A [8], [9] samples and synthetically generated zero mean Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) to predict the presence or absence of PU.

1.1 Autoencoders for Spectrum Sensing

An Autoencoder (AE) is an unsupervised ML algorithm comprising of an encoder and a decoder. The encoder part of an AE maps the input data into a hidden representation, and the decoder part reconstructs the input data from the hidden representation [10]. Being an unsupervised approach, AE networks are suitable when labelled data is limited and hence has been deployed in the domain of SS. In work [11], Cheng *et al.* proposed stacked AE-based models to perform SS of an Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) system. Xie *et al.* [12] designed a variational AE-based SS detector termed Unsupervised Deep Spectrum Sensing (UDSS) for a system of Quadrature Phase-Shift Keying (QPSK) modulated signals and Gaussian or Laplacian noise. Another work by Subray *et al.* [13] used deep, variational and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)-based AEs for SS in a system comprising of Wi-Fi and LTE signals. Motivated by the use of AEs in these works, we propose a deep AE-based SS detector in a system where the presence of PU signals is represented by the RadioML 2016.10A dataset [8] and the absence of PU is represented by synthetically generated noise samples.

2 Description of the Dataset Used

The publicly available RadioML 2016.10A dataset generated using GNU Radio software is used to represent the presence of PU signals. This dataset is a collection of 220,000 In-phase/Quadrature (I/Q) samples having a sample length of 128. These samples belong to 8 digital and 3 analog modulation schemes in a varying Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) range from -20 dB to +18 dB and are available as a pickle file. The digital modulation techniques are: 8-Phase-Shift Keying (8PSK), Continuous Phase Frequency Shift-Keying (CPFSK), Binary Phase-Shift Keying (BPSK), Pulse Amplitude Modulation-4 (PAM4), Gaussian Frequency-Shift Keying (GFSK), Quadrature Amplitude Modulation-16 (QAM16), QAM64, and QPSK while the included analog modulation schemes are: Amplitude Modulation-Double Sideband (AM-DSB), Amplitude Modulation-Single Sideband (AM-SSB), and Wideband Frequency Modulation (WBFM). There are 11,000 samples for each SNR value and 20,000 samples for each modulation type. For our use, the RadioML 2016.10A dataset is normalized in the range [0,1].

The absence of PU is represented by zero mean AWGN samples generated in Python. The noise samples are generated in I/Q pairs with a sample length of 128 and are normalized in the range [0,1]. For all simulations, an equal number of samples from the RadioML dataset representing the presence of PU and synthetically generated noise representing the absence of PU are taken to form a balanced dataset.

3 Autoencoder Architecture and Methodology

A deep AE network for unsupervised pretraining and a deep AE-based classifier which is fine-tuned to perform the binary classification of the dataset are proposed in this work. Multiple simulations are performed to finalize the model architecture and hyperparameters which result in the best classification performance. The deep AE model consists of two hidden layers in both the encoder and decoder with the encoder and decoder networks mirroring each other. The I/Q samples from the dataset are of dimension 128x2 and are flattened to a size of 256 before being provided as an input to the encoder. The encoder network maps this input to a hidden representation of size 64. The decoder network then reconstructs the I/Q data from the hidden representation. The architecture of the deep AE model is summarized in Fig. 1. As depicted by the time domain plot of the flattened I/Q input data in the figure, the input to the deep AE model can be either PU signal or noise. The deep AE model reconstructs the flattened I/Q samples of the PU signal or noise as shown in the output time domain plot in Fig. 1.

Another DNN model which performs binary classification of the dataset is defined. The weights of the encoder part of the trained deep-AE are retained. This classification model consists of the encoder network followed by a fully connected layer having 32 neurons and an output layer having a single neuron that generates the prediction about the status of the PU. The architecture of this model is summarized in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Architecture of the Deep Autoencoder.

The classifier model takes the flattened I/Q data as input and predicts whether the licensed user is present or absent.

Fig. 2. Architecture of the deep AE-based classifier model.

Based on the type of simulation, we always take equal number of PU signal and noise samples to keep the dataset balanced and the classifier unbiased. The dataset is divided into training, validation, and test sets in the ratio 8:1:1. Firstly, the deep AE network is trained without corresponding labels to reconstruct the input I/Q data. This process of unsupervised pretraining creates a compressed version of the input data after the encoder network and the decoder then produces a reconstructed version of the input data. The weights of the encoder network are retained, and a classification model is defined by adding two dense layers after the encoder layers. This classification model is then fine-tuned following a supervised approach to classify the input I/Q data as presence or absence of PU. Table 1. summarizes the hyperparameters used with the deep AE and classifier models. Both models have a batch size of 16 and are trained for 50 epochs by using a learning rate of 0.001 and Adam optimizer. The Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function is used for all layers except for the output layer of the classifier model which uses Sigmoid activation to predict the probability of the presence of the PU. No dropout is used for both models. The loss function used for the deep AE is mean squared error as the model is trying to reconstruct

Table 1. Hyperparameters used with the deep AE and classifier models.

Hyperparameter	Deep AE	Classifier Model
Epochs	50	50
Batch Size	16	16
Learning Rate	0.001	0.001
Activation function	ReLU for all layers	ReLU for all layers except output layer, Sigmoid for output layer
Dropout	None	None
Loss	Mean Squared Error	Binary Crossentropy
Optimizer	Adam	Adam

the input I/Q data. The classification model uses binary crossentropy loss as we are performing binary classification of the dataset.

4 Simulation Results

On using the entire RadioML 2016.10A dataset consisting of 220,000 I/Q samples of sample length 128 and an equal number of AWGN samples, the deep AE-based classification model achieves a test accuracy of 97.41%. We further utilize the models to obtain the test accuracies for different SNR values. For this, we separate the RadioML 2016.10A dataset for the 20 SNR values ranging from -20 dB to +18 dB. The RadioML 2016.10A dataset has 11,000 samples belonging to 11 different modulations for each SNR. Consequently, 11,000 noise samples are generated when performing a simulation with a particular SNR. The classification accuracies for different SNR values is depicted in Fig. 3. The test accuracy reaches 100% for the SNR values of 2, 4, 8, 10, 16 and 18 dB. The model performs poorly for the low SNR value of -20 dB.

Fig. 4. shows the classification performance of the proposed DNN-based approach for the 11 different modulation schemes. The RadioML 2016.10A dataset has 20,000 samples in a varying SNR range of -20 dB to +18 dB for each modulation type. Our model achieves 100% test accuracy for 8PSK, BPSK, PAM4 and QAM16 digital modulation schemes. It is observed that the model has a poor detection performance for AM-SSB which is an analog modulation scheme.

We further observe the time domain plots of the flattened I/Q input to the deep AE and the reconstructed input for an analog modulation technique (WBFM) and a digital modulation scheme (GFSK) for various SNRs. The deep AE model reconstructs the flattened I/Q samples of the PU signal or noise. The higher the variations between the reconstructed PU signal and noise I/Q samples, the easier it is for the classifier model to differentiate between the presence and absence of the PU. On the other hand, the higher the overlap between the reconstructed I/Q data for the PU and noise samples, the more difficult the classifier model finds to distinguish between the two classes. The plots of the inputs and outputs of the deep AE model for WBFM scheme and for various SNRs is shown in Fig. 5. For the low SNR values of -12 dB and -10 dB, both

Fig. 3. Classification performance of the proposed DNN-based approach for different SNR values.

Fig. 4. Classification performance of the proposed DNN-based approach for different modulation schemes.

WBFM and noise have scattered time-domain plots. Although ideally the classification accuracy for the classifier model must increase with an increase in SNR, the reconstructed WBFM and noise samples at -10 dB are more overlapped than for -12 dB, resulting in a lower classification accuracy at -10 dB. For the SNRs of 0 and 18 dB, the in-phase components of the WBFM signal have a slightly higher amplitude than the quadrature components giving the PU signal a unique reconstruction and thus making it more distinguishable than the reconstructed noise sample.

Fig. 6. depicts the input and reconstructed input for the deep AE model for GFSK modulation and noise samples at different SNRs. For the SNR values of -10 dB and -8 dB, the I/Q values of both GFSK signal and noise are scattered around similar amplitudes resulting in overlapping reconstructions. It can be observed from the output plots at the SNR values of 0 dB and 18 dB that the classifier model has high classification accuracies due to the visible difference in the reconstructed PU signal and noise samples.

Fig. 5. Input and output of the deep AE for WBFM signal and noise at various SNRs.

Fig. 6. Input and output of the deep AE for GFSK signal and noise at various SNRs.

5 Conclusion and Future Scope

In this work we explored the RadioML 2016.10A dataset and provided a description of various modulations and SNR ranges in the dataset. A deep AE-based approach for performing SS by treating it as a binary classification problem was proposed. A deep AE network is first pre-trained on the dataset without labels, and it reconstructs the input I/Q data. The weights of the encoder network of the AE are retained and a deep AE-based SS classifier is defined which comprises of the encoder layers of the encoder followed by a dense layer and an output layer. The fine-tuned classifier model achieves a test accuracy of 97.41% when the entire dataset is used. When analyzing the model performance for different SNR values and considering all modulation schemes, a classification accuracy of 100% is obtained for 6 SNR values: 2, 4, 8, 10, 16 and 18 dB. While observing the detector performance for various modulation schemes and considering all SNR values the classifier achieves a 100% detection performance for 8PSK, BPSK, PAM4 and QAM16 modulation techniques. Furthermore, we observed the time domain plots of the input I/Q data and reconstructed I/Q data for the deep AE model for an analog modulation scheme (WBFM) and a digital modulation scheme (GFSK). In future work, the performance of each of the 11 modulation schemes at specific SNR values would be analyzed to further enhance the classifier performance to achieve a higher detection performance for low SNR ranges and ensure that the detection performance increases consistently with an increase in SNR. It would be interesting to analyze the performance of the proposed approach by collecting a real-world dataset.

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